

Sphaeranthus indicus, *Sphenoclea zeylanica*, and *Nymphaea nouchali* [broadleaf weeds (dicots)]; *Monochoria aginalis* [broadleaf weeds (monocot)]; and *Marsilea quadrifolia* (fern).

In field experiments conducted at the Agricultural Research Station, Mannuthy, Trichur, during the 1985 rabi, the ecological requirements of the major weeds found in wetland rice were studied. Identification of weed species and their intensities of occurrence were observed in puddled and leveled rice fields under four situations: transplanted rice, wet sown rice, fallowing with 5 cm layer of water, and fallowing after the land is dried. The cultivar used was Jyothi (115 d). The experiment was laid out in randomized block design, replicated 5 times using 8- × 8-m plots.

Forty days after transplanting and wet sowing, the weed species that appeared in the experimental plots were identified and counted, *S. supinus* was found to be the most ubiquitous weed in either cultivated or fallowed fields. Occurrence was as high as 98 and 56.8 per square meter in transplanted and wet sown paddy crop (Table 1). *S. supinus* alone occupied 71% of the total weed population in transplanted rice, and 86% in wet fallow (Table 2). Wet sown rice favored the emergence of *C. iria*. *C. difformis* emerged as the major weed in wet sown rice, accounting for 43% of the total weed population. Both *C. difformis* and *S. supinus* constituted 79% of the total weed population in wet sown rice. *C. difformis* was appreciably suppressed in transplanted rice. Transplanting favored the emergence of *S. supinus* but suppressed *C. difformis* and *C. iria*. On the other hand, wet sowing suppressed *S. supinus* and favored *C. difformis* and *C. iria*. *F. miliacea* did not emerge under transplanting and wet fallowing conditions but appeared under wet sowing (6/m²) and dry fallowing (149/m²).

Broadleaf weeds, ferns and the grasses did not have widespread occurrence in any of the four situations studied. The spectrum of weed species occurring under wet sowing and dry fallowing was comparatively less (almost limited to 6)

Table 2. Percentage of weed species observed. Kerala, India.

Weed species	Percent per square meter			
	Transplanted rice	Wet sown rice	Wet fallow	Dry fallow
Grass				
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	1.7	0.0	0.8	0.1
Sedges				
<i>Scirpus supinus</i>	71.0	36.0	86.0	57.0
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	0.0	6.0	2.0	1.7
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	1.7	43.0	3.4	5.0
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	0.0	4.0	0.0	31.0
Broadleaf weeds (dicots)				
<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i>	0.6	0.0	0.0	5.0
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	7.0	1.5	2.0	0.0
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	0.9	0.0	1.4	0.0
<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i>	2.3	0.0	0.5	0.0
Broadleaf weeds (monocot)				
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	13.3	9.0	2.9	0.0
Fern				
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i>	1.6	0.0	0.4	0.0

compared to transplanting and wet fallowing with 9 or 10 species. Sedges occurring under transplanting, wet

sowing, wet fallow and dry fallow constitute 73, 89, 92, and 95%, respectively, of the total population. *J*

Integrated weed management in upland irrigated rice in Marathwada

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In Marathwada, acreage under upland

irrigated rice is increasing very fast. Losses due to weeds in upland rice are reported to be more severe than in transplanted rice. To evaluate weed control methods in upland irrigated rice, the use of herbicides with hand weeding was compared with higher rates of herbicides and hand weeding alone. The

Effect of herbicide treatment on grain yield and weed dry weight, showing additional profit over the control, Parbhani, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Increase in yield over control (%)	Dry weed weight (g/m ²)	Additional profit over control (\$/ha) ^c
Unweeded control	1.0	—	14.20	—
Recommended cultural practice, i.e. weeding and hoeing at 3 & 6 WAS ^a	2.0	106.3	3.39	106
1 hand weeding at 6 WAS	1.5	55.8	3.24	58
Butachlor				
1.50	1.4	51.0	8.63	35
1.00 ^b	1.8	85.9	1.00	83
Thiobencarb				
1.50	1.1	15.7	12.94	—
1.00 ^b	1.6	67.4	1.52	—
Pendimethalin				
1.00	2.1	115.1	1.55	—
0.75 ^b	2.2	134.2	1.10	—
Oxadiazon				
0.75	1.7	74.4	1.10	62
0.50 ^b	1.8	83.8	1.30	79
SE ±	0.2	—	0.70	—
CD at 5%	0.6	—	2.60	—
Mean	1.642	—	4.54	—

^aWAS = weeks after sowing. ^bWith one hand weeding at 6 WAS. ^cCost of butachlor, \$8 per kg; oxadiazon, \$10 per kg; thiobencarb and pendimethalin, not available; grain, \$13/g; straw, \$1/g; labor, \$0.61/day; bullock pair, \$2/day.

experiment was carried out in the Jayakwadi Command Area during kharif (Jul-Nov) 1984 at MAU. The dominant weeds were *Acalypha indica*, *Dinebra retroflexa*, *Corchorus aestuans*, *Digera arvensis*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Alysicarpus rugosus*, *Abutilon indicum*, and *Cyperus rotundus*.

Maximum grain yield (2.2 t/ha) was recorded with pendimethalin at 0.75 kg ai/ha supplemented with one hand

weeding at 6 wk after sowing (WAS). Grain yield was significantly superior to those with one hand weeding at 6 WAS and butachlor and thiobencarb application at 1.50 kg ai/ha. One hand weeding at 6 WAS, and applying butachlor and thiobencarb each at 1.50 kg ai/ha proved ineffective in controlling weeds in upland irrigated rice. Among the herbicides, pendimethalin was the most effective in

increasing grain yield, followed by oxadiazon (see table).

Economic analysis indicates that weeding and hoeing done twice at 3 and 6 WAS gave the highest profit. The price of pendimethalin is not available, but yields were higher than with the recommended cultural practice. When labor is short, preemergence application of pendimethalin at 1 kg ai/ha can be done, provided it is economical. *J*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

A new virulent strain of rice root-knot nematode from Agartala, India

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Root-knot nematodes are considered severe pests of upland rice. We surveyed rice nematodes in eastern India and found rice plants heavily infested with *Meloidogyne graminicola* in Agartala. These showed bigger galls on roots compared to those produced in Cuttack and Kerala. To know whether the Agartala population is different from the Cuttack and Kerala populations, a pot experiment was carried out. The three populations were inoculated into 5 rice varieties planted in 200 ml sterilized soil at 200 larvae/pot. Egg mass counts were taken after the first generation (21 d after inoculation) and compared (see table). The Agartala isolate reproduced equally well in all the five varieties while

Rice root-nematode egg masses (transformed values) 21 d after inoculation, India.

Variety	Egg masses (no.) from		
	Cuttack	Agartala	Kerala
Annapurna	4.88	4.05	6.52
Parijat	4.95	6.57	4.13
IR36	2.40	4.97	2.36
MW10	1.47	3.33	1.39
CR190	2.37	4.54	2.09
CD at 5%	1.20	ns	1.06
at 1%	1.71	ns	1.50

the two other isolates differed significantly in their reproduction. CR190, MW10, and IR36 were rated resistant to Cuttack and Kerala isolates while Annapurna and Parijat were susceptible. The Agartala isolate is considered as a new biotype for all the five varieties found susceptible to it. *J*

Plant nematodes in rice fields

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We surveyed 3 districts in Tamil Nadu, India (South Arcot, North Arcot, and Chingleput), for the occurrence of rice phytonema. We covered a total of 110 blocks: 28 in Chingleput, and 36 in each of the 2 other districts. The reported genera in the rice rhizosphere were *Hirschmanniella*, *Tylenchorhynchus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Criconemoides*, and *Hoplolaimus* spp. Their relative proportion in the soil and roots are

Proportion of different nematode genera in the soil and mts of rice.

Genus	Proportion in soil (%)	Proportion in roots (%)
<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	72.2	93.3
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i>	17.9	5.4
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	7.2	1.3
<i>Criconemoides</i>	2.0	—
<i>Hoplolaimus</i>	0.7	—

given in the table.

The predominant nematode is *Hirschmanniella* sp. which is found in both soil and roots. *Criconemoides* and *Hoplolaimus* spp. were not recovered from the roots. They occur in small proportion and were not economically important. *J*

Efficacy of nets to prevent bird damage to rice

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Nylon nets were placed over three rice varieties to determine their effectiveness against bird damage during the 1985 dry season.

Bird damage percentage in traditional varieties. Masapang, Victoria, Philippines, 1985 DS. * = significant difference between treatments 1 P = 0.05.